

Spectrophotometric Studies on Metal Chelates. Part IV. Gallium-sulphosalicylate Complex

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The instability constants of gallium-sulphosalicylate complex have been determined at three different temperatures, at two pH's, and in different ionic strengths from spectrophotometric measurements. At pH 3.0 and at ionic strength of 0.05, the values of K 's are $4.97 (\pm 0.15) \times 10^{-3}$, $4.11 (\pm 0.15) \times 10^{-3}$, and $3.00 (\pm 0.12) \times 10^{-3}$ at 20°, 29°, and 40° respectively. ΔH and ΔS are $-4.59 (\pm 0.21)$ kcal. and -35 ± 2.0 a.u. respectively.

In our earlier communications¹⁻³ the results of investigation of the aluminium-sulphosalicylate, aluminium-salicylate, and gallium-salicylate complexes have been reported. A search in the literature showed that the investigation of the gallium-sulphosalicylic acid system has not been attempted. It was observed that in presence of sulphosalicylic acid, gallium hydroxide is precipitated at a considerably higher pH than without it, thus indicating complex formation between the metal ion and the ligand. A detailed investigation by the spectrophotometric method was therefore undertaken. The composition and the instability constants of the complex have been determined at pH 3.0 and 3.5. The thermodynamic quantities, ΔF , ΔH , and ΔS , for the complex formation at pH 3.0 have also been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Gallium perchlorate was prepared by the method reported in a previous communication³. Other experimental details, such as, the adjustment of pH's, ionic strengths, and the temperature and the method used for calculating the instability constants have been reported earlier^{1,2}.

Gallium perchlorate solution (0.02M) was found to be transparent between 280 and 350 m μ in the pH range 1.5 to 3.5. The absorption maximum of sulphosalicylic acid around 300 m μ was found to be shifted to longer wave lengths in presence of Ga(ClO)₃, indicating complex formation. The shift became appreciable beyond pH 2.5 and was maximum between pH 3.0 and 4.0. Beyond pH 4.0, a thin precipitate, presumably of Ga(OH)₃, occurred. The detailed investigation of the gallium-sulphosalicylic acid system was therefore undertaken at pH 3.0 and 3.5.

The molecular composition of the complex was determined by Job's method at pH 3.0. Measurements were made at the total molarities 3.0×10^{-4} and 4.0×10^{-4} at the wave

1. Das and Aditya, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 473.
2. Nanda and Aditya, *ibid.*, 1963, 40, 660.
3. Das *et al.*, this *issue*, p. 739.

lengths 290, 310, and 315 μ . The plot of ' $\bar{D}$ ' against the mole fraction of Ga^{3+} are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The maximum or the minimum of the curves are found to occur at the composition ratio of 0.5 in every case, indicating the formation of a 1:1 complex. At pH 3.5, the composition of the complex has been assumed to be 1:1. This assumption appears to be justified as at this pH Ga^{3+} has been shown to form a 1:1 complex with salicylic acid³ and even at pH 4.0, Al^{3+} has been found to form a 1:1 complex with sulphosalicylic acid².

The extinction coefficients of the complex at 310 μ and both at pH 3.0 and 3.5 were determined by the method outlined in our earlier communications¹⁻².

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The average values were found to be 3594 and 3434 at pH 3.0 and 3.5 respectively. The extinction coefficients of the ligand at pH 3.0 and 3.5 were found to be 2036 and 1825 respectively.

The instability constants of the complex at 310 μ were determined at different ionic strengths. The results obtained are recorded in Table I.

DISCUSSION

Instability Constants.—At pH 3.0, the average instability constants at the ionic strengths 0.02, 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2 were found to be $2.46 (\pm 0.13) \times 10^{-3}$, $4.11 (\pm 0.16) \times 10^{-3}$,

7.46 (± 0.2) $\times 10^{-5}$, and 1.13 (± 0.15) $\times 10^{-4}$ respectively at ($29^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$). Again at pH 3.5 the average values at the ionic strengths 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2 were found to be 8.65 (± 0.17) $\times 10^{-6}$, 1.72 (± 0.08) $\times 10^{-5}$ and 3.12 (± 0.14) $\times 10^{-5}$ respectively at ($29^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$). In either case the instability constants were found to increase with ionic strength. We have here the instability constants of the gallium-sulphosalicylate complex at two different pH's. It is found that the incorporation of the hydrogen-ion concentration with a power of unity affords a fairly constant value of the equilibrium constants at the highest ionic strength. Though the agreement is not so good at other ionic strengths, the trend suggests that the equilibrium should be represented as:

where HR stands for $^-\text{O}_3\text{SC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{OH})\text{COO}^-$

TABLE I

Wave length = 310 μ , Cell length = 1 cm.

Ionic strength.	Temp.	pH	No. of readings taken.	Average value of the instability constant.
0.02	($29^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$)	3.0.	9	2.46 (± 0.13) $\times 10^{-5}$
0.05	"	"	9	4.11 (± 0.15) $\times 10^{-5}$
0.10	"	"	10	7.46 (± 0.20) $\times 10^{-5}$
0.20	"	"	10	1.13 (± 0.15) $\times 10^{-4}$
		pH = 3.0.		
0.05	20°	"	7	4.77 (± 0.18) $\times 10^{-5}$
0.05	40°	"	7	3.00 (± 0.12) $\times 10^{-5}$
		pH = 3.5.		
0.05	($29^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$)	"	9	8.65 (± 0.17) $\times 10^{-6}$
0.10	"	"	9	1.71 (± 0.08) $\times 10^{-5}$
0.20	"	"	9	3.12 (± 0.14) $\times 10^{-5}$

At pH 3.0 and at the ionic strength 0.05, the instability constants have been determined at temperatures 20° and 40°, besides those at $29^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. The average values at 20° and 40° are found to be 4.97 (± 0.18) $\times 10^{-5}$ and 3.00 (± 0.12) $\times 10^{-5}$ respectively. From these, the ΔH for reaction (1) has been determined from the slope of the plot of the logarithm of the instability constant against $1/T$ (Fig. 3). ΔH has thus been found to be -4.56 kcal. ΔH has been calculated with the help of the least square equation² and is found to be -4.59 (± 0.21) kcal. The agreement between the numerically calculated value and that obtained by the graphical method is quite good.

The values of ΔF 's at different temperatures, calculated on the basis of the equation

$$\Delta F = -RT \ln K \quad (2)$$

are 5772 (± 21), 6061 (± 22), and 6447 (± 26) calories at 20°, 29°, and 40° respectively. Using these values of ΔF 's and assuming that ΔH is constant over this temperature range, ΔS has been calculated. The average value of ΔS comes out to be -35 ± 1.6 e.u. Considering the overall uncertainties, we would prefer to put the deviation as ± 2 e.u., i.e., the value of ΔS as -35 ± 2 e.u.

On analysis of these thermodynamic functions, it is found that the contribution towards the stability of the complex is mainly due to the change in entropy. It may be mentioned that similar observations have been made by us in the case of the sulphosalicylate complex of aluminium and salicylate complex of gallium.

FIG. 3

Using the values of the instability constants of the complex at different ionic strengths, an attempt has been made to determine the thermodynamic instability constant ($\mu \rightarrow 0$) by different extrapolation methods. The results obtained will be communicated shortly.

The authors are thankful to the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs for the award of a grant-in-aid from the Fundamental Research Grant which made this investigation possible.

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Received April 16, 1963.